

Nutritional and Antinutritional Profiles of Four Distinct Varieties of *Oryza sativa* L.: Maharami, Lal Qilla, Owena, and Igbimo

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Abstract

Rice is a staple food consumed worldwide, with nutritional and antinutritional compositions varying across different varieties. This study aimed to assess the morphological, proximate, antinutritive, mineral, and vitamin compositions of four rice varieties: *Maharami*, *Lal Quilla*, *Owena*, and *Igbimo*. Standard methods were used for proximate, antinutritive, mineral, and vitamin analyses. Morphological analysis revealed varying grain sizes and weights, with *Lal Quilla* exhibiting the longest grains (7.8 mm) and *Maharami* having the highest 1000-grain weight (29.85 g). The proximate composition showed carbohydrate content ranging from 76.29% to 78.79%, with *Maharami* having the highest energy value (1473.89 kJ/100g). Antinutritive analysis revealed saponin and alkaloid contents between 1.42-3.43% and 2.67-12.76%, respectively, with *Lal Quilla* showing the highest phenol (27.84 mg GAE/g) and flavonoid content (24.64 mg QE/g). Mineral composition showed significant variations, with *Owena* having the highest potassium (4.018 mg/100g) and *Maharami* the highest iron (0.060 mg/100g). Vitamin content was consistent across all samples, with *Igbimo* having the highest Vitamin B₃ (2.618 mg/100g). These findings indicate the nutritional potential of these rice varieties, with *Maharami* and *Lal Quilla* being particularly rich in energy and bioactive compounds, respectively, making them promising for dietary applications.

Keywords: Proximate, antinutritive, mineral, *Oryza sativa*, vitamin.

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Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is one of the most extensively cultivated crops globally; it holds a unique and irreplaceable position in the diets of over half the world's population (Sen *et al.*, 2020). Its importance is

particularly pronounced in Asia, where it forms the backbone of culinary traditions and daily nutrition (Fukagawa and Ziska, 2019). Similarly, in many African countries, rice has become increasingly integral to food security and economic stability (De Vos *et al.*, 2023). This cereal grain, often termed the "staff of life," provides not just sustenance but also a sense of cultural identity and continuity for millions (Fuller and Lucas, 2021). The role of rice in global food systems is profound, as it contributes significantly to the intake of carbohydrates, the primary energy source for human metabolism (Mohidem *et al.*, 2022).

Carbohydrates, which comprise the bulk of rice's nutritional content, are essential for fueling bodily functions and maintaining energy levels (Clemente-Suárez *et al.*, 2022). Beyond carbohydrates, rice also supplies a range of essential nutrients, including proteins, vitamins (notably B vitamins) (Peña-Rosas *et al.*, 2019) and minerals like iron and zinc (Fukagawa and Ziska, 2019). These nutrients play a vital role in supporting growth, cognitive function and overall health (Gómez-Pinilla, 2008). The contribution of rice to global food security is underscored by its versatility and adaptability, allowing it to be grown in a wide range of environments, from rain fed lowlands to irrigated fields (Mohidem *et al.*, 2022). This adaptability has ensured its availability and accessibility, making it a reliable food source for millions of people, particularly in regions where food insecurity remains a pressing concern (Pawłak and Kołodziejczak, 2020).

It is essential to recognize that rice is not a monolithic crop (Sen *et al.*, 2020). The nutritional composition of rice is far from uniform, with significant variations observed across different varieties (Abera *et al.*, 2021). These variations are shaped by a complex interplay of genetic factors (Ali *et al.*, 2018), cultivation practices (Ishfaq *et al.*, 2023) and environmental conditions (Muller *et al.*, 2022). For instance, the genetic makeup of rice determines its potential nutrient content, including the levels of proteins, vitamins, and minerals (Zafar and Jianlong, 2023). Some varieties are bred for high yield, while others are selected for their nutritional qualities, such as higher levels of micronutrients like zinc and iron (Zafar and Jianlong, 2023), which are crucial for combating deficiencies in regions where rice is a staple. Cultivation practices also play a pivotal role in determining the nutritional value of rice (Mohidem *et al.*, 2022).

The methods used in planting, irrigation, fertilization and harvesting can influence the nutrient composition of the final product (Qiu *et al.*, 2022). For example, the application of fertilizers can enhance the levels of certain nutrients in the rice grain, but it can also lead to an increase in antinutritive factors if not managed properly (Purohit *et al.*, 2023). Organic farming practices, which avoid synthetic chemicals, have been shown to produce rice with higher antioxidant levels, contributing to better health outcomes (Bergman and Pandhi, 2022). These practices, combined with post-harvest processing methods such as milling and polishing, can significantly affect the nutritional profile of rice (Mohidem *et al.*, 2022). Polished white rice, for instance, has a lower nutrient content compared to whole grain brown rice, which retains more of its vitamins, minerals and dietary fiber (Zahra and Jabeen, 2020).

Environmental conditions, including soil quality, water availability and climate further contribute to the variability in rice's nutritional composition (Van Oort and Zwart, 2017; Ansari *et al.*, 2023).

Rice grown in nutrient-rich soils is likely to have a higher mineral content, while environmental factors such as drought or excessive rainfall can impact the levels of proteins and other essential nutrients in the grain (Sahasakul *et al.*, 2023). Climate change is also beginning to influence rice production, with shifting weather patterns affecting not only yields but also the nutritional quality of the rice produced (Joseph *et al.*, 2023). For example, rising temperatures and increased CO₂ levels have been shown to reduce the protein content in rice, which could have significant implications for populations that rely on rice as a primary protein source (Zhu *et al.*, 2018). Understanding these variations in the nutritional composition of rice is crucial for optimizing its role in human nutrition. This is particularly important in regions where rice constitutes a large portion of the daily diet and where nutritional deficiencies are prevalent (Zhao *et al.*, 2020; Zafar and Jianlong, 2023).

Selecting and promoting rice varieties with enhanced nutritional profiles could play a significant role in improving public health outcomes (Dipti *et al.*, 2012). For instance, biofortified rice varieties that are enriched with essential micronutrients like zinc and vitamin A have been developed to address specific nutritional deficiencies in vulnerable populations (Avnee *et al.*, 2023). These varieties offer a promising solution to malnutrition, particularly in children and pregnant women, who are mostly at risk (Shenoy *et al.*, 2023). The knowledge of how different factors influence the nutritional content of rice can guide agricultural policies and practices aimed at enhancing the nutritional quality of rice on a larger scale (Zafar & Jianlong, 2023). This includes breeding programs focused on developing rice varieties with improved nutritional profiles, as well as the promotion of sustainable farming practices that enhance nutrient content while minimizing antinutritive factors (Singh *et al.*, 2023). For consumers, understanding the nutritional differences between rice varieties can inform dietary choices, enabling them to select options that better meet their nutritional needs (Cabral *et al.*, 2024). The importance of rice in global food security and nutrition is undeniable, but maximizing its benefits requires a nuanced understanding of the factors that influence its nutritional composition (Mohidem *et al.*, 2022). By exploring the genetic, agricultural and environmental determinants of rice's nutrient content, we can better harness its potential to improve human health, particularly in regions where it is a dietary staple (Kobayashi *et al.*, 2023).

Figure 1. Igbimo Rice

Figure 2. Owena Rice

Figure 3. Maharami Rice

Figure 4. Lal Quilla Rice

Materials and Methods

Samples Collection and Treatment

The rice samples from four distinct varieties were used for this research. *Owena* rice, sourced from Owena in Ondo State, Nigeria, *Igbimo* rice, collected from Igbimo village in Ekiti State, *Maharami* basmati rice and *Lal Quilla* basmati rice were sourced from a reputable supermarket in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The dried samples were pulverized using an electric food blender and later stored in plastic containers with lids prior to the analysis.

Morphological Properties Analysis

The morphological characteristics of the collected rice grains, including length, width, and weight of 1000 grains, were measured following the method described by Nath *et al.* (2022). A digital caliper was used to determine the length and width of the grains with precision, while the weight was measured using an analytical balance.

Proximate Composition Analysis

The powdered rice samples were analysed to determine their proximate composition, which included measurements of moisture, ash, protein, fat, crude fibre, and carbohydrate content. Standard procedures outlined by the AOAC were employed for all assessments (Aremu *et al.*, 2012).

Moisture Content Determination

The grain (2.0 g) was weighed into a previously weighed crucible, and oven dried to a constant weight at a temperature of 105 °C. The amount of moisture determined in triplicate was carried out and expressed as loss in weight after cool weighing the sample.

Ash Content Determination

Ash content refers to the total mineral residue remaining after complete combustion of the sample at high temperatures, typically between 550 and 600 °C. The determination followed AOAC guidelines (Aremu *et al.*, 2012). Five grams of each rice sample were placed in separate crucibles and incinerated in a muffle furnace at 550 °C until a consistent ash weight was attained. The samples were cooled in a desiccator to prevent moisture uptake before final weighing, and the ash content was subsequently calculated.

Crude Fat Determination

Crude fat was extracted using an automated Soxhlet apparatus, following AOAC methods (Aremu *et al.*, 2012). Ten grams of sample were weighed and subjected to extraction using 25 mL of petroleum ether. The solvent was removed by oven drying, after which the samples were cooled in a desiccator and reweighed. The crude fat content was then calculated based on the weight difference (Eq. (1)).

$$\% fat = \frac{\text{Weight of fat extracted}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

Protein Content Determination

Protein analysis was performed using a wet digestion technique described by the AOAC (Aremu *et al.*, 2012). Three grams of the sample were digested in 25 mL of concentrated sulphuric acid with catalysts: 0.15 g titanium dioxide (TiO₂), 5 g potassium sulphate (K₂SO₄), and 0.15 g copper sulphate (CuSO₄). After digestion, the solution was diluted to 100 mL with distilled water, treated with 5 mL of sodium thiosulphate (Na₂S₂O₃) and 10 mL of 40% sodium hydroxide (NaOH), followed by boric acid. The

ammonia (NH₄⁺) released in the distillate was quantified via titration with 0.1 N hydrochloric acid. A blank sample (without protein) was also included. The nitrogen content obtained was multiplied by a conversion factor to determine the crude protein percentage. Thus:

$$\% \text{ crude protein} = \frac{ATV - TOTB \cdot 0.1NHCl \cdot 0.014 \cdot CF}{\text{Weight of sample}} \cdot 100 \quad (2)$$

where; ATV = actual titer value; TOTB = titer of the blank; CF = conversion factor; HCl = hydrogen chloride (mL).

Crude Fibre Determination

Crude fibre was measured using the AOAC protocol (Aremu et al., 2012). Five grams of the sample were introduced into a 500 mL Erlenmeyer flask, and 100 mL of a trichloroacetic acid (TCA) solution was added. The mixture was heated to boiling and refluxed for approximately 40 minutes, then slightly cooled and filtered using Whatman No. 4 filter paper (15.0 cm). The residue was rinsed with hot distilled water, transferred into a porcelain crucible, and oven-dried overnight at 105 °C. After cooling in a desiccator, the initial weight (W₁) was recorded. The sample was then incinerated in a muffle furnace at 500 °C for six hours, cooled again, and weighed (W₂). The crude fibre percentage was calculated using the appropriate formula (Eq. 3).

$$\% \text{ crude fibre} = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{\text{Weight of sample}} \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

Carbohydrates Content Determination

The carbohydrate content was determined by the difference in percentage:

$$\% \text{ carbohydrate} = 100 - (\% \text{ fiber} + \% \text{ protein} + \% \text{ ash} + \% \text{ moisture} + \% \text{ fat}) \quad (4)$$

Gross Energy

Gross energy (kJ per 100 g dry matter) was calculated based on the method of Ekanayake *et al.* (1999).

$$\text{Gross energy} = (\text{crude protein} \cdot 16.7) + (\text{fat} \cdot 37.7) + (\text{carbohydrates} \cdot 16.7) \quad (5)$$

Mineral Analysis

Mineral content in the rice flour samples was evaluated through wet digestion procedures, following the standard protocols outlined by AOAC (2005). Potassium and calcium concentrations were measured using a flame photometer (Model 405, Corning, UK), whereas levels of copper, magnesium, iron, and zinc were assessed using an atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Perkin–Elmer Model 403, Norwalk, CT, USA). All mineral concentrations were expressed as milligrams per 100 grams of sample, with each variety analyzed in triplicate.

Anti-Nutrient Content Determination

The levels of various antinutritional compounds—namely tannins, alkaloids, saponins, phytates, oxalates, total phenols, and flavonoids—were quantified in the rice flours based on the methodologies described by Afiukwa et al. (2011) and Minussi et al. (2003).

Vitamins Analysis

The assessment of vitamins A, thiamine, riboflavin, and niacin was conducted using analytical techniques recommended by AOAC (2005).

Statistical Analysis of the Samples

Fatty acid content for each sample was estimated by applying a conversion factor of 0.8 to the measured crude fat value (i.e., crude fat \times 0.8). Energy content was computed by summing the products of carbohydrate, protein, and fat contents with their respective energy conversion factors: carbohydrate \times 17 kJ, protein \times 17 kJ, and fat \times 37 kJ. Standard deviations (SD) were calculated from three replicates to account for variation in proximate composition data.

Results and Discussion

The morphological characterization of rice grains length, width and weight as displayed in Table 1 provides essential insights into their quality, processing potential and overall market value. *Lal Quilla* has the longest grains length of 7.80 mm, followed closely by *Maharami* 7.00 mm, while *Owena* has a medium length of 6.80 mm and *Igbimo* has the shortest grains length of 5.00 mm. Grain length is a significant factor in determining the rice's quality; longer grains are often associated with higher quality, better consumer appeal and potentially higher market prices (Adu-Kwarteng *et al.*, 2003). *Lal Quilla*'s length suggests it could be considered a premium variety, while *Igbimo*, with the shortest grains, might be viewed as lowest in quality. Width also plays a crucial role in determining rice quality *Igbimo* has the widest grains at 3.50 mm, indicating a potentially higher starch content, which can lead to a softer texture when cooked (Chen *et al.*, 2022). In contrast, *Lal Quilla* has the narrowest grains at 2.50 mm, which might contribute to a firmer texture and potentially less starch content. The balance in grain width, as seen in *Owena* rice and *Igbimo*, suggests a moderate texture, which could be appealing in a broad range of applications.

The weight of 1000 grains is a key indicator of grain density and potential yield. *Maharami*, with the highest weight of 29.85 g, suggests that it has the most densely packed grains, which could translate to better milling yield, higher nutritional content, and overall superior quality. In comparison, *Igbimo*, with the lowest weight of 18.72 g, indicates less dense grains, possibly resulting in lower milling efficiency and nutritional value. The weights of *Maharami* and *Lal Quilla*, being similar, suggest moderate quality, with acceptable yields and nutritional content. These morphological parameters are critical in determining rice quality, influencing its marketability, consumer acceptance, and economic value (Custodio *et al.*, 2019). The present research is entirely consistent with the findings of Pillai *et al.*, (2020), who reported that the average length, width and weight of the rice varieties in the sample were 6.20, 2.67, and 19.36, respectively.

Table 1. Morphological Characteristics of the Samples

Sample	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Weight of 1000 grain (g)
<i>Maharami</i>	7.00	3.00	29.85
<i>Lal Quilla</i>	7.80	2.50	20.76
<i>Owena</i>	6.80	3.00	20.91
<i>Igbimo</i>	5.00	3.50	18.72

The proximate composition is a critical indicator of the nutritional quality and suitability for consumption of any foodstuff (Custodio *et al.*, 2019). The moisture content of rice is vital as it influences the shelf life, texture and its palatability (Chen *et al.*, 2022). As shown in Table 2, *Maharami* has the highest moisture content of 11.80%, followed by *Lal Quilla* (10.85%), *Owena* (9.80%), and *Igbimo* (9.39%). Lower moisture content, as seen in *Owena* and *Igbimo*, generally suggests better storage stability and reduced susceptibility to microbial growth, which is advantageous for long-term storage (Alp and Bulantekin, 2021). However, higher moisture content, like in *Maharami* can lead to a softer texture which might be preferred in some culinary applications.

Dietary fiber is essential for digestive and helps in maintaining bowel regularity. It also has a role in reducing cholesterol levels and controlling blood sugar levels (Barber *et al.*, 2020). *Igbimo* stands out with the highest fiber content of 5.15%, indicating its potential benefits for digestive health. *Maharami* and *Owena* also have relatively high fiber content (2.46% and 2.33%, respectively), while *Lal Quilla* has the lowest fiber content of 0.92%. The higher fiber content in *Igbimo* makes it particularly suitable for individuals looking to increase their fiber intake for health reasons while *Lal Quilla* with lower fiber content, may be better suited for individuals requiring a lower-fiber diet. Ash content represents the total mineral content in the rice and is crucial for determining its nutritional value (Wisetkomolmat *et al.*, 2022). *Maharami* has the highest ash content of 1.56%, followed by *Lal Quilla* (1.18%), *Owena* (0.96%), and *Igbimo* (0.54%). A higher ash content indicates a greater concentration of minerals such as calcium, potassium and magnesium (Datta *et al.*, 2019), this make *Maharami* potentially more beneficial from a micronutrient perspective. However, the lower ash content in *Igbimo* suggests a lower mineral content, which may reduce its nutritional benefits in terms of mineral intake.

Crude fat content is an important source of energy and essential fatty acids (Kaur *et al.*, 2012). *Lal Quilla* has the highest fat content at 0.96%, which contributes to its higher energy value. *Maharami* and *Owena* have moderate fat content (both at 0.57%), while *Igbimo* has the lowest fat content at 0.38%. The higher fat content in *Lal Quilla* may enhance its energy density and flavor, making it preferable for individuals needing more calories, while the lower fat content in *Igbimo* could be beneficial for those on low-fat diets. Protein is essential for growth, repair and overall health (Carbone and Pasiakos, 2019). The protein content across the samples is relatively similar with *Owena* having the highest crude protein content of 7.55%, followed by *Lal Quilla* (7.53%), *Igbimo* (7.40%) and *Maharami* (7.32%). This similarity suggests that all samples are good sources of plant-based protein, which is essential for vegetarian or vegan diets. *Owena*, with the highest protein content may be slightly more beneficial for those prioritizing protein intake. Carbohydrates are the primary energy source in rice (Fukagawa and Ziska, 2019). *Owena* has the highest carbohydrate content of 78.79%, closely followed by *Lal Quilla* (78.56%), *Igbimo* (77.14%), and *Maharami* (76.29%). The higher carbohydrate content in *Lal Quilla* and *Owena* contributes to their higher energy values, making them ideal for energy-demanding activities or as a staple in diets requiring high energy intake. The energy value reflects the overall calorie contribution of the rice (AghaAlikhani *et al.*, 2013). *Lal Quilla* has the highest energy value of 1473.89 kJ/100 g, followed by *Owena* 1463.37 kJ/100 g, *Igbimo* 1426.14 kJ/100 g, and *Maharami* 1417.78 kJ/100 g. The values obtained in this study were comparable to the gross energy value of 105 high-yielding Indian rice varieties, ranging from 1422.56 to 1489.5 kJ/100 g (Longvah *et al.*, 2010).

Table 2. Proximate Composition of Rice Varieties (% Dry Weight Basis)

Parameters	Maharami	Lal Quilla	Owena	Igbimo
Moisture content (%)	11.80	10.85	9.80	9.39
Fiber content (%)	2.46	0.92	2.33	5.15
Ash content (%)	1.56	1.18	0.96	0.54
Crude Fat (%)	0.57	0.96	0.57	0.38
Crude protein (%)	7.32	7.53	7.55	7.40

Carbohydrate content (%)	76.29	78.56	78.79	77.14
Energy (kJ/100g)	1417.78	1473.89	1463.37	1426.14

The antinutritive composition of *Maharami*, *Lal Quilla*, *Owena*, and *Igbimo* rice reveals variations in saponin, alkaloid, flavonoid, phenol, tannin, phytate, and oxalate contents (Table 3). These antinutrients, often perceived negatively due to their potential to interfere with nutrient absorption, also have health-promoting properties when consumed in moderation (Petroski and Minich, 2020). Saponins are known for their bitter taste and ability to form foams in aqueous solutions (Timilsena *et al.*, 2023). They have been linked to both positive and negative effects on human health. High saponin content can decrease protein digestibility and nutrient absorption, but saponins also have cholesterol-lowering properties and can stimulate the immune system (Singh *et al.*, 2023). *Igbimo* has the highest saponin content of 3.43%, indicating a stronger potential for these effects, followed by *Owena* (2.25%), *Lal Quilla* (1.62%), and *Maharami* (1.42%). The higher saponin content in *Owena* and *Igbimo* may be more beneficial for those seeking the cholesterol lowering effects of saponins, but could also result in a more pronounced bitter taste, which might affect palatability.

Alkaloids are nitrogen-containing compounds that can be toxic in high amounts, but they possess therapeutic properties such as, pain relief and antimicrobial effects (Heinrich *et al.*, 2021). *Lal Quilla* has an exceptionally high alkaloid content of 12.76%, which may offer significant health benefits but could also pose a risk of toxicity if consumed in large quantities. *Owena* follows with 7.54%, *Igbimo* with 3.77%, and *Maharami* with the lowest content at 2.67%. The high alkaloid content in *Lal Quilla* suggests it could have potent biological effects, potentially making it more suitable for medicinal purposes, but less ideal for regular dietary intake due to the risk of toxicity. Flavonoids are known for their antioxidant properties, which help protect the body from oxidative stress and reduce the risk of chronic diseases such as heart disease and cancer (Panche *et al.*, 2016). *Lal Quilla* has the highest flavonoid content of 24.64 QE/mg/g, followed closely by *Maharami* (23.98 QE/mg/g). *Igbimo* has a moderate content of 19.15 QE/mg/g, while *Owena* has the lowest 11.48 QE/mg/g. The high flavonoid content in *Maharami* and *Lal Quilla* suggests that these rice varieties could offer superior antioxidant protection, making them beneficial for individuals looking to boost their intake of these health-promoting compounds.

Phenolic compounds also have strong antioxidant properties and contribute to the prevention of oxidative damage in the body (Tungmunthum *et al.*, 2018). *Lal Quilla* has the highest phenol content of 27.84 GAE/mg/g making it potentially the most effective in combating oxidative stress. *Maharami* follows with 14.39 GAE/mg/g, while *Owena* and *Igbimo* have similar phenol contents of 13.95 and 13.83 GAE/mg/g, respectively. The high phenol content in *Lal Quilla* reinforces its potential health benefits, particularly for those at risk of conditions related to oxidative stress, such as cardiovascular diseases. Tannins are polyphenolic compounds that can bind to and precipitate proteins, which can inhibit the absorption of iron and other nutrients. However, they also have antioxidant and antimicrobial properties (Huang *et al.*, 2017). The tannin content across all samples is relatively similar, with *Igbimo* having the highest at 9.36 GAE/mg/g and *Maharami* the lowest at 9.15 GAE/mg/g. This uniformity suggests that all samples have comparable astringency and potential health benefits associated with tannins.

Phytates are known as antinutrients because they can chelate minerals such as calcium, iron and zinc, reducing their bioavailability. However, they also possess antioxidant properties and may have a role in cancer prevention (Petroski and Minich, 2020). *Maharami* has the highest phytate content of 4.88%, followed by *Igbimo* (3.75 %), *Lal Quilla* (3.02%), and *Owena* with the lowest 2.54%. The higher phytate content in *Maharami* may be a concern for mineral absorption but could offer greater antioxidant protection, making it more suitable for those who can offset mineral loss through dietary means. Oxalates can bind to calcium, leading to the formation of kidney stones in susceptible individuals. However, they are also naturally occurring compounds in many healthy foods (Mitchell *et al.*, 2018). *Maharami* has the

highest oxalate content of 2.75%, which could be a concern for those prone to kidney stones, while *Lal Quilla*, *Owena*, and *Igbimo* have lower contents 2.39%, 1.88%, and 2.05%, respectively. The lower oxalate content in *Owena* may make it a safer option for individuals with a history of kidney stones. The antinutritive composition of these rice samples highlights a balance between beneficial and potentially harmful effects. *Lal Quilla* stands out for its high content of alkaloids, flavonoids, and phenols, suggesting potent health benefits but also possible risks. *Maharami* and *Igbimo* offer moderate antinutrient levels, with *Maharami* having the highest phytate content and *Igbimo* the highest saponin content. *Owena*, with the lowest overall antinutrient content, might be preferred for individuals seeking to minimize their intake of these compounds while still gaining some health benefits. The values obtained in this study were comparable to the value of antinutritive composition of rice obtain by Aremu *et al.* (2024).

Table 3. Antinutritive Composition of Different Rice Samples

Parameters	Maharami	Lal Quilla	Owena	Igbimo
Saponin (%)	1.42±0.19	1.62±0.11	2.25±0.07	3.43±0.06
Alkaloid (%)	2.67±0.06	12.76±0.12	7.54±0.14	3.77±0.32
Flavonoid (QE/mg/g)	23.98±0.06	24.64±0.07	11.48±0.06	19.15±0.06
Phenol (GAE/mg/g)	14.39±0.07	27.84±0.06	13.95±0.07	13.83±0.08
Tannin (GAE/mg/g)	9.15±0.00	8.64±0.04	8.66±0.00	9.36±0.00
Phytate content (%)	4.88±0.08	3.02±0.08	2.54±0.22	3.75±0.18
Oxalate content (%)	2.75±0.12	2.39±0.03	1.88±0.08	2.05±0.05

The mineral composition of *Maharami*, *Lal Quilla*, *Owena*, and *Igbimo* rice reflects significant variation in the concentrations of essential nutrients, highlighting the differences in nutritional value among the samples (Table 4). Minerals play crucial roles in human health and food quality, influencing both the nutritional profile and the potential health benefits of the rice. Potassium (K) is a vital mineral that regulates fluid balance, muscle contractions, and nerve signals in the body. It is also essential for maintaining proper heart function (Udensi and Tchounwou, 2017). In this study, *Owena* has the highest potassium content at 4.018 mg/g, indicating that it may provide better support for cardiovascular health and electrolyte balance compared to the other samples. *Lal Quilla* follows closely with 3.335 mg/g, while *Maharami* has a slightly lower content of 3.168 mg/g. *Igbimo* rice has the lowest potassium content at 2.011 mg/g, suggesting that it may be less effective in supporting potassium-dependent physiological functions. This difference in potassium content could influence the overall health benefits provided by these rice samples, especially for individuals needing higher potassium intake, such as those with hypertension. The values obtained were comparable to the potassium content of other rice varieties of Kerala studied by Deepa *et al.* (2008).

Copper (Cu) is another essential trace mineral, playing a key role in the formation of red blood cells, maintaining healthy nerves, and supporting immune function (Weyh *et al.*, 2022). Both *Maharami* and *Igbimo* rice contain 0.010 mg/g of copper, making them superior sources of this mineral compared to *Lal Quilla* and *Owena*, which have 0.005 mg/g and 0.002 mg/g respectively. Adequate copper intake is important for preventing anemia and maintaining overall immune health (Burkhead and Collins, 2021). The higher copper content in *Maharami* and *Igbimo* rice might contribute to better support for these physiological functions, making them more valuable for individuals with copper deficiency or increased copper needs. The values obtained were comparable to the copper content of other rice varieties studied by Pillai *et al.* (2020). Magnesium (Mg) is crucial for bone health, muscle function, and energy production. It is also involved in over 300 enzymatic reactions in the body (Fiorentini *et al.*, 2021). *Maharami* has the highest magnesium content of 0.110 mg/g, which is significantly higher than the other samples. This suggests that *Maharami* could be more beneficial in supporting metabolic processes, bone health and reducing the risk of magnesium deficiency-related conditions such as osteoporosis and muscle cramps.

The other samples *Lal Quilla*, *Owena*, and *Igbimo* rice have much lower magnesium contents, ranging from 0.053 mg/g to 0.056 mg/g, indicating that they may contribute less to these important health aspects. The values obtained were comparable to the content of other rice varieties studied by Balasubramanian *et al.* (2019).

Calcium (Ca) is essential for building and maintaining strong bones and teeth, as well as supporting nerve function, muscle contraction and blood clotting. *Igbimo* rice has the highest calcium content of 0.056 mg/g, closely followed by *Owena* at 0.053 mg/g. *Lal Quilla* has a slightly lower content of 0.005 mg/g, while *Maharami* has the lowest calcium content of 0.003 mg/g. The values obtained were comparable to the calcium content of other rice varieties studied by Pillai *et al.* (2020). Iron (Fe) is critical for the production of hemoglobin, the protein in red blood cells that carries oxygen throughout the body (Abbaspour *et al.*, 2014). *Lal Quilla* has the highest iron content of 0.060 mg/g, indicating that it could be more effective in preventing iron deficiency anemia and supporting oxygen transport in the body. *Igbimo*, with 0.037 mg/g, and *Maharami*, with 0.019 mg/g, also provide moderate amounts of iron, while *Owena* has the lowest iron content of 0.006 mg/g. The higher iron content in *Lal Quilla* makes it particularly valuable for individuals at risk of iron deficiency. The values obtained were comparable to the iron content of other rice varieties studied by Pillai *et al.* (2020).

Zinc (Zn) is essential for immune function, DNA synthesis and wound healing (Lin *et al.*, 2017). *Maharami* has the highest zinc content of 0.032 mg/g, suggesting that it could provide better support for immune health and skin integrity. *Owena*, *Igbimo* and *Lal Quilla* have lower zinc contents, with *Lal Quilla* having the lowest at 0.014 mg/g. The higher zinc levels in *Maharami* highlight its potential role in enhancing immune defense and promoting overall health. This present research is entirely consistent with the findings of Brar *et al.* (2011).

Table 4. Mineral Analysis (mg/g)

Parameters	Maharami	Lal Quilla	Owena	Igbimo
Potassium (K)	3.168±0.260	3.335±0.021	4.018±0.049	2.011±0.091
Copper (Cu)	0.010±0.000	0.005±0.001	0.002±0.001	0.010±0.000
Magnesium (Mg)	0.110±0.000	0.053±0.001	0.054±0.001	0.056±0.001
Calcium (Ca)	0.003±0.000	0.005±0.000	0.053±0.000	0.056±0.001
Iron (Fe)	0.019±0.001	0.060±0.071	0.006±0.001	0.037±0.001
Zinc (Zn)	0.032±0.001	0.014±0.005	0.021±0.001	0.018±0.004

Vitamins are essential micronutrients required for various biological functions and their presence in food directly impacts health outcomes (Ofoedu *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2022). Vitamin A is essential for vision, immune function, and skin health (Tang *et al.*, 2009). For populations that consume rice as a major part of their diet, even small differences in vitamin content can have significant implications for public health. The vitamin analysis of the four rice varieties (*Maharami*, *Lal Quilla*, *Owena*, and *Igbimo*) reveals subtle but significant differences in the concentrations of vitamins A, E, B1, and B3 (Table 5). For Vitamin A, the concentrations were as follows: *Maharami* (0.126 ± 0.000 mg/kg), *Lal Quilla* (0.126 ± 0.000 mg/kg), *Owena* (0.128 ± 0.000 mg/kg), and *Igbimo* (0.131 ± 0.000 mg/kg). The Vitamin A levels are fairly consistent across the varieties, with *Igbimo* showing a slightly higher concentration which could make it a slightly better option for enhancing these specific nutritional benefits. The concentrations of Vitamin E were *Maharami* (0.035 ± 0.000 mg/kg), *Lal Quilla* (0.035 ± 0.000 mg/kg), *Owena* (0.035 ± 0.000 mg/kg) and *Igbimo* (0.036 ± 0.000 mg/kg). The Vitamin E content is almost similar among the varieties, with *Igbimo* showing a marginally higher value. Vitamin E is a powerful antioxidant that helps protect cells from oxidative damage, contributing to skin health and immune function (Maggini *et al.*, 2007). Given the uniformity of the results, all varieties offer comparable levels of antioxidant protection, with *Igbimo* again showing a slight edge.

For Vitamin B₁ (Thiamine), the concentrations were Maharani (0.420 ± 0.001 mg/kg), *Lal Quilla* (0.422 ± 0.001 mg/kg), *Owena* (0.427 ± 0.001 mg/kg), and *Igbimo* (0.436 ± 0.001 mg/kg). There is a progressive increase in Vitamin B₁ content from *Maharani* to *Igbimo*. Vitamin B₁ is crucial for energy metabolism and the proper functioning of the nervous system (Mrowicka *et al.*, 2023). *Igbimo*, with the highest concentration of Vitamin B₁, is the most beneficial variety for supporting energy metabolism and neurological health, followed by *Owena*, *Lal Quilla*, and *Maharani*. The Vitamin B₃ (Niacin) concentrations were Maharani (2.523 ± 0.004 mg/kg), *Lal Quilla* (2.530 ± 0.002 mg/kg), *Owena* (2.563 ± 0.005 mg/kg), and *Igbimo* (2.618 ± 0.007 mg/kg). Vitamin B₃ content is highest in *Igbimo*, followed by *Owena*, *Lal Quilla*, and *Maharani*. Vitamin B₃ is important for DNA repair, skin health and lowering cholesterol levels (Doroftei *et al.*, 2020). *Igbimo* stands out for its higher Vitamin B₃ content, making it the most beneficial for skin health and cardiovascular support among the varieties analyzed. Overall, *Igbimo* consistently shows the highest concentrations of the vitamins analyzed, suggesting it may be the most nutritionally superior variety among the four. *Owena* comes next, followed by *Lal Quilla* and *Maharani*. The slight variations in vitamin content among these varieties could influence their suitability in addressing specific nutritional deficiencies in populations that rely heavily on rice as a dietary staple. The values obtained in this study were comparable to the value of antinutritive composition of rice obtain by Devi *et al.* (2015); Chaudhari *et al.* (2018) and Longvah *et al.* (2017).

Table 5. Vitamin Analysis (mg/g)

Parameters	<i>Maharami</i>	<i>Lal Quilla</i>	<i>Owena</i>	<i>Igbimo</i>
Vitamin A	0.126±0.000	0.126±0.000	0.128±0.000	0.131±0.000
Vitamin E	0.035±0.000	0.035±0.000	0.035±0.000	0.036±0.000
Vitamin B ₁	0.420±0.001	0.422±0.001	0.427±0.001	0.436±0.001
Vitamin B ₃	2.523±0.004	2.530±0.002	2.563±0.005	2.618±0.007

Conclusion

The comparative analysis of four rice samples *Maharami*, *Lal Quilla*, *Owena*, and *Igbimo* revealed notable differences in their morphological, proximate, antinutritive, mineral, and vitamin compositions. *Igbimo* had the smallest grains but exhibited the highest fiber and saponin contents, while *Lal Quilla* had the highest alkaloid and phenol concentrations. *Owena* showed the highest potassium and flavonoid levels, highlighting its potential antioxidant capacity. Nutritionally, *Maharami* had the lowest moisture content and highest energy value. All samples showed similar vitamin compositions, with *Igbimo* containing the highest Vitamin B₃. These findings suggest distinct nutritional and phytochemical benefits for each variety, contributing to their diverse applications in food and health industries. The choice of the particular rice for consumption may depend on the nutritional need of individual consumers and what variety of rice would best meet the need.

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